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Protocol for a Literary Study of *Sarvatantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhant* in *Brihatrayee* and *Laghutrayee* along with their Applied Aspects

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ABSTRACT

Introduction:

Ayurveda, the ancient Indian system of medicine, is founded on eternal principles known as *Siddhantas*. Among these, *Sarvatantra Siddhant* (universally applicable principles) and *Pratitantra Siddhant* (context-specific principles) play a crucial role in both theoretical understanding and practical application. These principles are elaborated extensively in classical texts including the *Brihatrayee* and *Laghutrayee*, yet a comprehensive literary analysis of their categorization and application remains underexplored.

Materials and Methods:

This study is designed as a qualitative literary analysis. Primary classical texts such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridayam*, *Sharangadhara Samhita*, *Bhavaprakasha Samhita*, and *Madhavidana* are included. The research involves identification, compilation, and analytical categorization of references to *Sarvatantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhantas* from these texts. Their practical implications are also studied and systematically presented.

Results :

The study aims to provide a structured categorization of *Siddhantas*, enhance understanding of their clinical relevance, and demonstrate how foundational principles can be applied in contemporary Ayurvedic practice. It is anticipated that the findings will offer improved frameworks for diagnostic and therapeutic planning based on ayurvedic principles.

Discussion and Conclusion :

A deeper exploration of these *Siddhantas* is expected to reinforce the foundational

knowledge of Ayurveda and support its practical integration in healthcare. The study also aims to contribute to academic and clinical settings by offering a systematic approach to classical principles, thus strengthening the bridge between theoretical knowledge and practical application in Ayurveda.

Keywords: *Siddhanta, Sarvatantra, Pratitantra, Ayurvedic Principles, Literary Study, Applied Aspects.*

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Introduction

The survival of any science depends on how strong are the basic principles from which it is formed, and Ayurveda is one of the best examples to prove that. As the whole tree depends on its root, likewise the entire ayurveda also depends on its eternal principles. Hence, Ayurveda is said to be *Shashvata* [1] and *Nitya*. Ayurveda is a Science which deals with preventive & curative aspects. In the emergence of any new science, *Siddhanta* plays an important role. In Ayurveda, there are many *siddhantas* which form a strong foundation for the emergence and survival of this life science. Based on these *siddhanta*, the main aim of Ayurveda i.e., “*Swasthasya Swasthya Rakshanam Aturasya Vikara Prashamanam*” [2] have been discussed in the *samhitas*. *Acharya Charaka* described the concept of *Siddhanta* [3] in *Rogabhishakjiteeya Adhyaya* of *Vimana Sthana*. These are broadly classified into four types namely *Sarvtantra*, *Pratitantra*, *Adhikarana* and *Abyupagama Siddhanta*.

Ayurveda, an ancient and comprehensive science, is rooted in its eternal principles known as *Siddhanta*. These principles serve as the foundation for understanding and practicing Ayurveda effectively. Among these, *Sarvtantra Siddhant* (universally accepted principles) and *Pratitantra Siddhant* (context-specific

principles) hold immense significance as they provide a structured framework for the application of Ayurvedic knowledge.

The *Brihatrayee* (major classical texts) and *Laghutrayee* (minor classical texts) contain vast references to these *Siddhantas*, emphasizing their importance in diagnosis, treatment, and health maintenance. By conducting a detailed literary study of these principles and their applied aspects, this research aims to enhance the understanding of their role in clinical practice and theoretical knowledge.

Aim and Objectives

Aim

To conduct a literary study of *Sarvtantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhant* in Ayurvedic literature, along with their applied aspects.

Objectives

1. To review the concepts of different *Siddhantas* as mentioned in *Brihatrayee* and *Laghutrayee*.
2. To categorize *Siddhantas* mentioned in Ayurveda under *Sarvtantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhantas*.
3. To analyze their practical applications for better understanding and clinical relevance.

Research Question

What are the different types of *Sarvtantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhant* in *Brihatrayee* and *Laghutrayee*, and what are their applied aspects?

Significance of the Study

1. Provides a deeper understanding of foundational Ayurvedic principles.
2. Helps students and practitioners approach Ayurveda in a structured and systematic manner.
3. Enhances diagnostic, prognostic, and treatment planning skills based on *Siddhantas*.
4. Aids in validating and updating Ayurvedic concepts for modern-day application.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Inclusion Criteria

The study will include the following authoritative classical texts:

- *Charaka Samhita*
- *Sushruta Samhita*
- *Ashtanga Hridayam*
- *Sharngadhara Samhita*
- *Bhavaprakasha Samhita*
- *Madhava Nidana*

Exclusion Criteria

- Commentaries or translations in regional languages not directly derived from the classical Sanskrit versions.

Methodology

1. **Identification of Materials:** Reading, analyzing, and sorting Ayurvedic texts to extract references on *Sarvtantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhantas*.

2. **Compilation:** Listing relevant contexts and references from the *Brihatrayee* and *Laghutrayee*.

3. **Analysis:** Evaluating *Siddhantas* from multiple perspectives and understanding their implications.

4. **Presentation:** Systematically presenting findings with practical applications in clinical practice.

Study Design

This research is a literary study that involves qualitative analysis of classical Ayurvedic texts.

Review of Literature

Several prior studies have addressed *Chaturvidha Siddhanta* broadly. Notable contributions include:

1. Sakhare et al. (2019) – Conceptual understanding and applied interpretation from Maharashtra.
2. Raghuwanshi et al. (2019) – Critical overview with applied focus from Madhya Pradesh.
3. Gupta et al. (2021) – Analytical study on classification and clinical value from Uttar Pradesh.
4. Bishnoi et al. (2021) – Comprehensive literary synthesis based on classical Ayurveda from Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh.

While these works provide foundational perspectives, this study specifically aims to deepen the understanding of the *Sarvtantra* and

Pratitantra doctrines individually, an area less explored in previous literature.

Expected Outcomes

1. Improved understanding of *Sarvatantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhantas* in clinical practice.
2. Structured categorization of *Siddhantas* for easy reference and application.
3. Enhancement of theoretical knowledge and practical skills in Ayurveda.

Declaration

This study will be completed within the stipulated time frame as prescribed by the Institute for *Ayurved* Studies and Research, Kurukshetra.

Conclusion

The study of *Sarvatantra* and *Pratitantra Siddhantas* emphasizes the significance of fundamental Ayurvedic principles in diagnosis, treatment, and health maintenance. A systematic understanding of these *Siddhantas* allows physicians to apply their knowledge

effectively in clinical practice, ensuring the advancement of Ayurveda. By integrating theoretical insights and practical applications, this research aims to contribute significantly to the field of Ayurveda.

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